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 Sample Name: Proszki

C_Si 9_1

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 9.41 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Error %
C K	97.4	0.00	98.3	5.1
O K	1.9	0.02	1.4	12.8
Si K	0.7	0.02	0.3	6.5

/Lukasiewicz 25.02.25/Proszki/C_Si 9_1/Full Area 1/

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35.5 Live Time(s): 299.9 Amp Time(μs): 0.96 Resolution:(eV) 131.6

Det: Element-C2B